

Integrated modeling of the Lower Tapi basin using SWAT

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Abstract The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) is a globally used integrated watershed model for studying sediment, hydrology, land use, climate change, in-stream water quality, and other water management actions on water quality and quantity. The present research aims to Hydrological Modelling of Lower Tapi Basin using SWAT from Ukai dam to Surat city. Surat is one of India's most densely populated cities, located at the tail portion of the Tapi River. One of the biggest flood occurred in the year of 1998 and 2006. The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) was used to establish Rainfall-Runoff relationship for the Lower Tapi Basin. The Lower Tapi basin runoff is estimated using the SWAT model, which combines GIS data with an attribute database. SWAT a physical based Semi-distributed parameter designed to predict runoff, effect of soil and anticipate the effect of land management approaches. SWAT model is developed for the base line scenario for 1998-2017. SWAT-cup is used to calibrate and validate the SWAT model. Then, using 19 years of daily precipitation as well as daily maximum and lowest temperature data. A SWAT simulation is run for each day to determine future runoff for the associated rainfall. On a daily time scale, the model was calibrated at the Mandvi gauging site. The observed flow data was used to identify sensitivity values, which were then calibrated. For auto-calibration and validation, the SWAT-CUP SUFI-2 software was employed. The calibrated model can be utilized for further in-depth study, such as water resource management and climate and land use change impact assessments.

Keyword Integrated modelling, Hydrology, SWAT Model, SWAT-CUP SUFI-2

Introduction

The most significant intrinsic of water resources development and administration programmers is understanding a basin's water balance [1]. Water balance equations can be used to quantify major hydrological processes. Any effort to develop water resources requires a full understanding of how these physical elements interact with hydrological component. Because hydrologic processes are so complex, it's critical to have a thorough understanding of them, which is why watershed models are so popular [1]. The majority of watershed models essentially simulate precipitation transformation into runoff, sediment discharge, and nutrient losses.

Integrated watershed models are models that provide a holistic picture of the numerous hydrologic processes [2]. There are a variety of physically based Semi-distributed models that are integrated. SWAT has been regarded as the most promising and computationally efficient among them by academics (Neitsch et al., 2005) [3]. As a result, an attempt has been made in this work to identify the most sensitive SWAT model parameters and to evaluate the significant hydrologic components of a river basin with an emphasis on water conservation and management.

The main goals of this study are to use the SWAT model to analyses the Rainfall-Runoff conduct of the Lower Tapi Basin, to simulate the discharge using SWAT-CUPs with the sequential uncertainty fitting (SUFI-2) algorithm, and to undertake sensitivity testing of the model parameters in terms of improving the model's actual prospects in simulating runoff.

Description of Model

The USDA Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS) and Texas a&MAgriLite Research collaborated to create the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), a public domain model. The SWAT model is a watershed model with a long-term, continuous simulation. It's made to predict how management affects water, sediments and agricultural chemical yields on a regular basis. This model was created in the early 1990s. With the passage of time, the SWAT model's development process continues to address many emergent difficulties in hydrological modelling. Various tools, such as different hydrological response units, auto irrigation and fertilization options, nutrition cycling routine, Bacteria transfer routine, and so on, were introduced to the model during its development. Water and sediment circulation can be examined and projected with the help of this model. Runoff in urban catchments can be estimated using this model. The entire catchment region has been separated into sub-catchments in order to use the model in a real-world setting. The sub catchments are further separated into minor Hydrological Response Units (HRU) based on land use and land cover similarities, as well as soil management techniques [2]. The basin's hydrology can be separated into two phases: routing phase and land phase. Simulation of the hydrological cycle integrating whole water circulation in the basin is necessary for better estimation and forecasting of water, sediment circulation, and other parameters from the basin.

Study Area

The Tapi Basin is the Deccan plateau's northernmost basin, located approximately between 72 33' and 78 17' east longitudes and 20 N to 22 N latitude. The Tapi River is the Peninsula's second greatest westward draining interstate river. It begins at an elevation of 752 meters near the Multai reserve forest in the Betul district of Madhya Pradesh. The river's total length is 724 kilometers, with the first 282 kilometers flowing through Madhya Pradesh and 54 kilometers defining the state's common boundary with Maharashtra. It flows across Maharashtra for 228 kilometers before entering Gujarat. The Tapi River flows across Gujarat for 214 kilometers before joining the Arabian Sea at the Gulf of Cambay after passing through Surat.

The Tapi basin is divided into sub-basins: the Upper Basin (29,430 sq. km) up to the Hatnur intersection of the Purna with the major Tapi, the Middle Tapi Basin (25,320 sq. km) from Hatnur to the Gidhade gauging site, and the Lower Tapi Basin (25,320 sq. km) again from the Gidhade gauging site up to the sea (10,395 sq.km) [4].

The Lower Tapi Basin, which includes Surat, is located between the Ukai Dam and the Arabian Sea. One of the worst floods in Surat's history occurred in the years 1998 and 2006. The flood of 2006 is recognized as a severe calamity that resulted in the widespread destruction of structures worth INR 20 billion and impacted people's lives, with roughly 300 people dying as a result of the devastating floods [4]. Figure 1 depicts a map of the Lower Tapi basin's location.

Fig. 1 Location map of Lower Tapi basin

Methodology and Data Collection

Methodology

SWAT necessitates a large number of spatial and temporal inputs. SWAT, being a semi- model, must process, aggregate, and analyses these data geographically utilizing GIS technologies. As a result, the model has been integrated with GIS software as a downloadable ArcSWAT for ArcGIS supplementary extension to make it easier to use. In flow chart Figure 2, the methodology for runoff modelling at the basin outlet using SWAT is depicted.

Fig. 2 Methodology of Rainfall-Runoff modelling

Data Collection

Rainfall Data

The daily rainfall data required as input for SWAT analysis. For this study, daily rainfall data from 8 rain gauge stations in the Lower Tapi basin was chosen from a total of 13 rain gauge stations with at least 20 years of data, and these rain gauge

stations were gathered through the Gujarat State Water Data Centre (SWDC). The location and name of each SWDC rain gauge station are listed in Table 1. The position of the raingauge station is depicted in Figure 3.

Table 1 Rain gauge station selected for study in Lower Tapi basin

Station Name	District	Latitude	Longitude
Ambli	Surat	21.400	73.408
Godsamba	Surat	21.279	73.231
Kadod	Surat	21.217	73.216
Kholvad	Surat	21.275	72.948
Rander	Surat	21.223	72.792
Ukai	Surat	21.256	73.580
Uteva	Surat	21.350	73.215
Zankhvav	Surat	21.443	73.319

Fig. 3 Location of Raingauge Station

Runoff Data

The river flow data for the Lower Tapi basin was also acquired from the State Water Data Centre (SWDC) in Gujarat. Daily streamflow data are used to calibrate and validate the SWAT model. Runoff data from one river gauge station in the study area, i.e., the Lower Tapi Basin, namely, Mandvi, is available.

Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

A digital elevation model (DEM) is a three-dimensional depiction of a terrain created from elevation data. DEM was retrieved from the Bhuvan ISRO website. DEM (Cartosat-1, CartoDEM Version-3 R1) with a resolution of 30mx30m was downloaded from Bhuvan (<https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/home/index.php>). Using ArcGIS10.5, the data sets are masked and projected in UTM projection. The DEM is used to define the longest reaches, drainage surfaces, and stream network of the watershed and sub-basins. Figure 4 shows the digital elevation model of Lower Tapi basin.

Fig. 4 Digital Elevation Model

Landuse Landcover Classification

The Landuse data was created from the LANDSAT 8 image (acquired on October 2020). The information was taken from the USGS Archive. The downloaded file contains seven bands. The picture is then converted into the correct projection using ArcGIS, just as the Digital Elevation Model with about the same dataset. The supervised classification technique was used for picture classification by distinguishing unique signatures present in the Tapi lower basin, and the image was then translated to systematic form in ArcGIS to make it acceptable with

ArcSWAT. Water, pasture, Agricultural Land-Generic, Mixed Forest, and Residential are among the major classifications. Figure 5 depicts the land use map of the Tapi lower basin, while Table 2 shows the area covered by various land use types.

Table 2 Tapi Basin LULC classes

Sr. No.	Category	Area (km ²)	Area of the Watershed (percent)
1	Water	710.8409594	38
2	Pasture	386.9089199	21
3	Agricultural Land-Generic	614.9602592	33
4	Mixed Forest	86.63310304	5
5	Residential	53.88316237	3
Total		1853.226404	100

Fig. 5 Map of Land Use

Soil Map

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO/UNESCO) provided a soil map with a geographical resolution of 1: 50, 000, 00. The soil data from the Tapi Lower Basin has been separated into three groups. The texture of the soils is clay loam, loam, and clay. Figure 6 shows the soil map of study area (Lower Tapi basin).

Fig. 6 Soil Map of Study Area

Uncertainty Analysis and Calibration

SUFI-2 can be used for uncertainty analysis and calibration, and it can simultaneously analyze a high degree of complexity and observed values from a significant number of sampling locations. It also requires the least number of simulation experiments to generate accurate uncertainty data and calibration, and that can be connected directly with SWAT-CUP by an interaction. By comparing observed stream flows at the Mandvi gauge station with daily simulated stream flows, the SWAT model has indeed been optimized for daily modelled stream flows. The model was run for a 20-year period (1998–2017). Model sensitivities, uncertainty analysis and calibration were performed using the SWAT-CUP (uncertainty programs and calibration) interface. For the most sensitive

parameters, the model has been calibrated. Many origins of errors, including generating parameters (for example, precipitation), conceptual model, variables, and observed values, are taken into consideration in SUFI-2 (Abbaspour et al., 2004) [5]. The d and p-factor (Abbaspour et al., 2007) [6] were used to quantify the accuracy of calibration and uncertainty measures with combination to the Nash-Sutcliffe (NSE) and coefficient of correlation (R2). In contrast to these criteria, (Moriassi et al., 2007) [7] used the NSE and coefficient of correlation between observations and final best simulations to determine goodness of fit. NSE is a standardized statistic that determines the magnitude of remaining variables compared to actual variation in the data (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970) [8]. The NSE could be computed using equation 1,

$$(1)$$

Calibration of a SWAT Model

SWAT Model Predictions Evaluation and Performance

For a period of time, the SWAT model, which was calibrated and verified, was used to simulate hydrological elements of the Lower Tapi basin (1998-2017). Reduce the disparity between measured and expected daily stream flows, and correlate estimated daily amounts to measured stream flow values that were used to calibrated the model.

The SUFI2 algorithm of SWAT CUP was used to perform auto validation and calibration in this investigation. Using the SWAT Model text input file as a main source of information. The next step is to denote the observed stream flow. Another step is to set number of parameter that would be more sensitive to Tapi Lower basin. The iterative procedure used by SUFI-2 reduces the attribute values after every repetition. The number of simulations in each iterative procedure has been set to 500. After the number of iterations had been set, all of the statistical factors could be computed every time, and the best simulation could be seen in the output results as the suitable statistical value outcome.

Analysis of Results

The SWAT hydrological model for the lower Tapi basin is used, as well as model runs using SWDC observed climate data to validate and calibrate this model using actual flows. A sensitivity analysis on twelve factors was undertaken in order to determine the significant factors controlling the hydrologic processes for river discharge computing given by the SWAT model. Variable sensitivity was calculated using Global sensitivity analysis in the SWAT CUP SUFI-2 software. The values of sensitive parameters are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 The values of Sensitive Parameters

Name of the parameter	Fitted value	Minimum value	Maximum value
V_CH_N2.rte	0.0943	0.0829	0.2488
R_OV_N.hru	0.2526	-0.0547	0.3357
V_GW_DELAY.gw	22.5551	-130.2715	256.6315
R_SOL_AWC (.).sol	-0.0891	-0.3477	0.0507
V_EPCO.hru	0.8068	0.2873	0.8626
V_SLSUBBSN.hru	144.6588	61.575	164.7847
R_CN2.mgt	-0.1647	-0.3166	0.0278

Results of Calibration and Validation

The SWAT model in the Lower Tapi basin was calibrated using the SUFI-2 approach. Plots of daily observed and simulated stream flow were generated to evaluate the model performance based on visual comparison. For some of the more intense storm events, the peak stream flow is over or under predicted (Figure 7). Figure 7 shows that all high peaks are underestimated, and in many cases, a significant difference between observed and simulated flow can be noticed. Figure 7 depicts each day calibration of observed and simulated flow for the Lower Tapi basin.

Fig. 7 Calibration of Observed and Simulated Flows for the Lower Tapi Basin on a Daily basis

Validation was carried out with the same parameter value ranges and 500 simulations. A seven-year validation period was used (2011-2017). The daily validation plot between observed and simulated flow is shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8 Validation of Observed and Simulated Flow for the Lower Tapi Basin on a Daily Basis

Results and Discussions

By referring relevant literature (Kh. Gorgij, A. Dehvari and M. R. Dahmardeh Ghaleno, 2020) [9]; (Geethu Krishnan, Kuduluru Srinivas Kumar, Rejani R., 2020) [10]; (Moriassi, D. N., C. G. Rossi, J. G. Arnold, and M. D. Tomer, 2012) [11]; Van Griensven, T. Mexiner, S. Grunwald, T. Bishop, M. Diluzio, R. Srinivasan, 2005) [12] and SWAT documentation (Neitsch et al., 1970) [8], a set of model parameters for sensitivity analysis was chosen. To validate and calibrate the model, the parameters with the highest sensitivity were used. The most vulnerable criteria are those indicating Surface Response, Sub-Surface Runoff, and Basin Response, according to the findings. The SWAT hydrological parameters SCS runoff curve number CN2, CH N2, SOL AWC, OV N, EPCO, ESCO, ALPHA BF, GW DELAY, GWQMN, REVAPMN, SURLAG and SLSUBBSN are crucial for the model's success. SCS runoff curve number (CN2), Average slope length (SLSUBBSN), Ground delay (GW DELAY), Manning's "n" value for the main channel (CH N2), Plant uptake compensation factor (EPCO), Manning's "n" value for overland flow (OV N) and Available water capacity of the soil layer (SOL AWC) are the most sensitive parameters for the USRB, according to the sensitivity analysis. Tables 4 for daily periods give the results of statistical evaluation criteria used to check model performance.

Table 4 Performance Evaluation of a Statistical Model for the Lower Tapi Basin on a Daily Basis.

Statistical Parameter	R ²	NSE
Calibration (2001-2010)	0.87	0.86
Validation (2011-2017)	0.83	0.82

Results and Discussions Conclusions

Observed stream flow data was used to calibrate and validate the SWAT model. During the Lower Tapi basin's calibration and validation periods, the SWAT model worked admirably. For calibration and validation, twenty-year discharge data is separated into two equal halves. To determine the important parameters affecting the flow, a sensitivity analysis is carried out. The flow was auto-calibrated from 2000 to 2010 using daily observed and simulated flows. Validation of flows between 2011 and 2017 has been completed. The R² coefficients of determination for daily calibration and validation were 0.87 and 0.83, correspondingly, showing that the calibrated and observed daily flows are in good agreement. Overall, the model response well to the simulation of streamflow for the Lower Tapi basin. The model is therefore suitable to simulate runoff behavior of Lower Tapi basin.

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